

Research Data Policy

PhotoNanoMat Group

Erlangen Center for Interface Research and Catalysis
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen Nürnberg (FAU)

Florian M. Wisser, CC-BY 4.0

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0. Preamble

This policy is based on FAU's research data policy,¹ the research data policy of the Bösmann group² at the Institute of Chemical Reaction Engineering (CRT) and the DFG's guidelines for handling research data.

It is supplemented by the RDM instructions for doctoral students and the respective project-specific data management plan established at the CRT and the Erlangen Center for Interface Research and Catalysis (ECRC) at FAU.

1. Area of application

This policy applies to all employees of the PhotoNanoMat Group. It applies to all research activities. Applicable law and contracts with third parties are restrictive.

In research collaborations, the handling of research data will be determined before the start of the project. This policy should preferably be applied unless the partners have equivalent or higher requirements. In particular, agreements should be reached on the publication of research data.

2. Legal aspects

2.1. Copyright owner

The resulting research data includes several categories of data types, which may result in different right owners. For data from routine analysis (order measurements), the right of use lies with the group. For works in the sense of the Copyright Act (UrHG) and related rights, the rights are held by the creators of the works.

2.2. Data privacy

Normally, research data is not linked to sensitive personal data. This will be checked before publication.

2.3. Assignment of rights

In the case of research data and research results covered by the UrHG or related property rights, a permanent, non-exclusive right of use of these data should be transferred to the group in the supervision agreement. The transfer is voluntary. If this permanent transfer of rights has not been granted from the outset and as a general rule, it must be obtained on a case-by-case basis.

3. Type and scope of data

Research data are generated and stored in all projects of the PhotoNanoMat group. The expected data volume can vary considerably depending on the project and the type of experiments performed (see Table 1, Appendix A.2). On average, a data volume of < 100 MB per person per working day is expected. Data and metadata will be stored at the Regionales Rechenzentrum Erlangen (RRZE, computing centre) in compliance with the FAU data policy³ as well as the FAIR principles.⁴ Typical research data of the group include:

¹ <https://www.cdi.fau.de/en/about/policies-und-workingpapers/>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10796217>

³ <https://www.fau.info/fdm-policy>

⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

- **Raw data**, e.g. description of experiments, log files of instrument runs, NMR, GC, XRD, ... measurements
- **Processed data**, e.g. integrated GCs (with peak assignment where appropriate), analysed NMR spectra, ...
- **Results**, e.g. Arrhenius plots, activation energies, identity/purity of compounds or diagrams of various types derived from a large amount of processed data, e.g. plots of productivity, turn over number/frequency, stability,

Along with the raw data format (instrument format), the research data will also be provided in an interoperable form (see Table 1, Appendix A.2). This can be generic CSV type files or free formats such as JCAMP. These data types are described by metadata. Wherever possible, standard text file formats are used to represent analytical information, such as the Crystallographic Information File (*.cif) or the Adsorption Information File (*.aif).

4. Documentation and data quality

4.1. Electronic laboratory notebook and data handling

Each researcher in the group is required to process research data using an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN), so that all data from one experiment are connected to this experiment. This ensures that the data can be re-used by the group at any time and can also be easily prepared for publication. The data will be stored and secured as described in section 5.1. Depending on the type of research data different software tools might be used for data processing including MATLAB or Origin. The used software tools and codes will be described in the ELN using metadata, including the version and associated input/configuration files.

4.2. Documentation and metadata

To ensure that the research data comply with the FAIR principles, each experiment will be given a unique identifier (ID) that will serve as file name, if required with an extension to identify different e.g. characterisation carried out on a material (see below). The identifier will consist of a three-letter code unique for each researcher (%%%), a two-letter code unique for each project (\$\$) and a number code unique for each material and batch (XXXX-XX): “%%%-\$\$-XXXX-XX”. This identifier will also be used to describe all associated raw data, processed data, results and metadata to allow a direct link to the experiment in the ELN. If necessary, an extension will be added to the identifier to uniquely identify the type of characterization performed, e.g. “%%%-\$\$-XXXX-XX_IR” in the case of an IR experiment. Likewise for instruments individual ID will be used to precisely link an experiment to an instrument with a given calibration.

Metadata in an interoperable format will be used to describe all the information necessary to reproduce the data, in particular when conversion of the data into an interoperable form results in the loss of such information (see Table 1, Appendix A.2). Metadata thus provide information on:

- Experimental reaction conditions
- Chemical purity and supplier
- Instrument setup and measurement parameters
- Data handling and processing
- Software codes and parameters used for analysis

In the case of publication in a journal, meta data are provided with the raw and/or processed data in a data repository (**Figure 1**) but will also be provided in the experimental section / supporting information file.

Figure 1. Scheme linking information of an experiment including its identifier (ID) with the corresponding raw data from characterization and reactions and with processed data, including information on software. The meta data generated at each level are also linked together within the ELN / archive. The raw, processed and meta data belonging to a journal article are additionally stored in a data repository giving them a unique persistent identifier (PID).

4.3. QA processes

QA and QC process will be implemented throughout the whole process of data generation. On instruments (certified) standards with known properties (concentration, retention time, surface area, ...) will be analysed regularly. To ensure data quality, all new members will be brief on the data policy and get details on data handling in the project. Likewise, when sharing research data with other groups, the group does not give write access to the raw data. Instead, a copy of the dataset will be created and will be used for further processing and keep the original secure from accidental changes.

5. Storage and technical archiving the project

All research data will be stored securely and retrievably for a period of at least 10 years after the end of a project. The security of the storage is achieved through technical measures such as redundant array of independent disks (RAID), automatic backup and offsite storage. Retrievability is achieved by describing the data using metadata and the use of ELN (**Figure 1**).

In principle, research data should be published as early as possible, as comprehensively as possible and sensible, and as permissively as possible; exceptions to this are third-party claims to confidentiality, planned patent applications, etc. (section 5.2) .

5.1. Data storage and security

Data is stored on the measurement device or on the control computer. From there it is automatically or manually transferred to one of the local data servers (RAID1). This data server updates the central data server at the RRZE (RAID6) every five minutes.

The central server is fully backed up to HDD on a monthly basis (three-disk rotation, cold storage). A full backup to HDD is performed annually, the discs are stored offline for > 10 years.

An ELN is used for further data processing and use. The ELN is hosted at the RRZE on a mirrored RAID with daily backups (disk or tape). In addition, the analysed data of the group members is typically

stored on the personal network drive (local, RAID1). From there it is automatically transferred to the central server in the data centre (RAID6). Access to the server-based storage and the ELN is controlled via login to the system via SSO, provided by the computing centre.

5.2. Data sharing, re-use and long-term availability

FAU will ensure the long-term archiving of the research data via its Competence Center for Research Data and Information (FAU CDI).⁵ All research data will be made available for subsequent use by the group in accordance with the FAIR principles. This will be done locally and without publication (see also section 4, **Figure 1**).

For data sharing within collaborative projects, the handling of research data will be determined before the start of the project. This policy should preferably be applied unless the partners have equivalent or higher requirements. In particular, agreements should be reached on the publication of research data, on access to data after the collaboration has ended, and the sharing of project data with other partners in future projects.

Research data belonging to publications will be made publicly available (for exception see below), immediately after acceptance of the publication. Where possible, raw data and data resulting from processing should be made available together, up to and including the result. To ensure persistent access to these datasets, they will be made publicly available in repositories preferentially on Zenodo, RADAR, FAUDataCloud and OPEN FAU. A persistent identifier (PID), e.g. a digital object identifier (DOI), will be generated for each of those datasets.

Bachelor's/Master's theses: Bachelor's and Master's theses are not required to be published under the examination regulations, and the copyright remains with the author.

Dissertation: There is a publication requirement for dissertations as part of the Doctoral Regulations.⁶ Doctoral students are encouraged to publish their work openly, for example in OPEN FAU, and to deposit their research data in a repository in accordance with this policy.

Research data will not be made directly publicly available or after a defined retention period in cases such as:

- conflicting third party rights, e.g. from contracts with industrial partners (may require retention period)
- publication could affect an ongoing project or a follow-up project
- where a patent application is in progress or has not yet been definitively ruled out (may require retention period)
- a planned publication in a peer-reviewed journal would be affected
- the quality of the data is too low, or the data are incomplete.

5.3. Accessibility and licences

The preferred access is Open Access. The preferred licence is CC BY. If required by external licence terms, the licence will be adjusted.

⁵ <https://cdi.fau.de>

⁶ https://www.doc.zuv.fau.de//L1/Promotion_und_Habilitation/Promotion_Tech/englisch/Faculty_Doctoral_Regulations_FPromO_Tech_20130121_idF_20201223.pdf

6. Responsibilities and resources

The group leader is responsible for the management of all research data generated in the group, including data curation after the project.

The collection and primary processing of research data is usually carried out by the researcher working on the project (bachelor or master student, PhD candidate, post-doctoral researcher). Each new group member is instructed by the group leader on how to handle research data.

6.1. Data steward / Data custodian

The roles “data steward” and “data custodian” follow the definition provided by the FAU-policy *“Konzept zur Sicherstellung der langfristigen Verfügbarkeit von Forschungsdaten: data stewards und data custodians”*.⁷ Each researcher, especially PhD students, is the data steward of her or his project and is supported by the group leader.

The group leader is the data steward for the group. The function of the data custodian is assumed by the group leader. As soon as appropriate structures are in place, data access and data inheritance will be regulated.

6.2. Data selected for persistent access

Prior to publication, the data will be checked. The group leader is responsible for checking the data.

6.3. Re-use of third party data

When data from third parties is reused in the group, researchers are required to cite the data appropriately and to comply with the terms of the licence.

6.4. Costs

For each project, the cost of the ELN (including training) is set by the FAU Competence Center for Research Data and Information (FAU CDI) to a sum of 1000€ (500€/project + 500€ training).⁸

⁷ <https://gitlab.rrze.fau.de/cdi/admin/policies-working-paper/-/blob/master/workingpaper/data-steward-custodian.md>

⁸ <https://www.cdi.fau.de/services/kosten-und-leistungsverzeichnis/#elektronisches-laborbuch-eln-fuer-forschung>

7. Validity of policy, review, contact

This policy is valid as of 14 July 2025.

The policy will be reviewed at least annually to ensure that it is up to date. Changes will be made as necessary.

contact:

Dr. Florian M. Wisser

Erlangen Center for Interface Research and Catalysis

Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

florian.wisser@fau.de

7.1. Appendix

A.1. Assignment of rights

The rights to data and works for use in research and education are to be transferred to the group.

Suggested agreement:

I [name] hereby transfer to the PhotoNanoMat group at the ECRC the non-exclusive right of use, unrestricted in time, space and content, to data and works that have been or will be created in the context of my [dissertation, other activity] at the Chair.

This transfer does not apply to works that are licensed differently (eg. CC BY-NC-ND-SA or a written and unambiguous statement like “© [date, name] All rights reserved”).

This agreement may be terminated at any time with effect for the future.

A.2. Data types

Table 1. Overview of standard analytic techniques used, together with the corresponding instrument, data size for raw data, original format as well as information on data processing into interoperable formats.

Data Source Class	Instrument	av. Size per measurement / MB	original format(s)	convertible to open format(s)	loss of information on conversion
DSC	Netzsch DSC 204F1 Phoenix	1	*.ngb-sd7	*.txt	no
DVS	Surface Measurement Systems	1	*.dat	*.xlsx	no
Elemental analysis	Elementar UniCube CHNSO			*.xlsx	--
ESR	Bruker EMX micro	0.05	*.dta, *.dsc, *.spc, *.par	*.txt	yes
fluorescence	Avantes	0.1	*.RWD8	*.txt	no
gas physisorption	Micromeritics ASAP 2000	1	*.smp	*.xls, *.aif	yes
gas physisorption	Quantachrome Autosorb 1	0.05	*.qps	*.csv, *.txt, *.aif	yes
gas physisorption	Quantachrome Quadrasorb	0.05	*.qps	*.csv, *.txt, *.aif	yes
gas physisorption	Quantachrome NOVA	0.05	*.qps	*.csv, *.txt, *.aif	yes
density	He-Pycnometry	0.01	*.txt		--
ICP	Spectro	0.05	*.pdf-report		--
IR	JASCO FT/IR-4100	0.05	*.jws	*.txt, *.csv	no
mercury porosimetry	Thermo Fisher Pascal 140 & 440	0.5	*.140 / *.440	*.xls	yes
NMR (liquid state)	JEOL ECX-400	1	*.jdf	JCAMP-DX	yes
NMR (solid state)	Agilent Varian 500WB	> 1, for 1D spectra > 100, for 2D spectra	folder folder	JCAMP-DX, *.txt *.pdf	yes yes
Oxygen Meter	PyroScience, FireStingO2	0.5	*.txt		--
powder XRD	PANalytical, Empyrean	0.05	*.xrdml	*.csv	no
SEM	diverse	1	*.tiff		--

single analysis	crystal diverse			*.cif	no
TEM	diverse	10	*.tiff		--
TG	TA, Hi-Res TGA 2950 Thermogravimetric Analyzer	0.1	*.001	*.txt	no
UV-Vis	JASCO V-650	0.05	*.jws	*.txt, *.csv	no